

ON TRAJECTORY OF A QUADRATIC STOCHASTIC OPERATORS IN S^2

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ishda ikki o'lchamli simpleksda aniqlangan novolterra kvadratik stoxastik operatorni o'rganamiz. Ya'ni, simpleksda aniqlangan kvadratik stoxastik operatorini ko'rib chiqamiz. Ikki o'lchamli simpleksda aniqlangan novolterra kvadratik stoxastik operator uchun qo'zg'almas nuqtalar topilgan.

Abstract: In this article, we study the novolterra quadratic stochastic operator defined on a two-dimensional simplex. That is, we consider the quadratic stochastic operator defined on a simplex. It is shown that for the novolterra quadratic stochastic operator defined on a two-dimensional simplex, the vertices of the simplex are fixed points.

There are many systems which are described by nonlinear operators. A quadratic stochastic operator (QSO) is one of the simplest nonlinear cases.

Let $E = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ be a finite set and the set of all probability distribution on E

$$S^{m-1} = \left\{ x = (x_1, \dots, x_m) \in \mathbb{R}^m : x_i \geq 0, \sum_{i=1}^m x_i = 1 \right\} \quad (1)$$

be the $(m-1)$ -dimensional simplex. *quadratic stochastic operator*. The QSO is a mapping $W : S^{m-1} \rightarrow S^{m-1}$ of the form

$$x'_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^m P_{ij,k} x_i x_j, \quad k \in E, \quad (2)$$

where $P_{ij,k}$ are coefficients of heredity such that

$$P_{ij,k} \geq 0, \quad \sum_{k=1}^m P_{ij,k} = 1, \quad \forall i, j \in E. \quad (3)$$

and we suppose that the coefficients $P_{ij,k}$ do not change for any permutation of i, j .

The novolterra QSO $W : S^2 \rightarrow S^2$ is:

$$W : \begin{cases} x'_1 = x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 - x_1 x_2 - x_1 x_3, \\ x'_2 = 3x_1 x_2 + x_2 x_3, \\ x'_3 = 3x_1 x_3 + x_2 x_3. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Let a face of the simplex S^2 be the set $\Gamma_\alpha = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_i = 0, i \notin \alpha \subset \{1, 2, 3\}\}$.

Let the set $\text{int } S^2 = \{\mathbf{x} \in S^2 : x_1 x_2 x_3 > 0\}$ and let the set $\partial S^2 = S^2 \setminus \text{int } S^2$ be the interior and the boundary of the simplex S^2 , respectively. Let $\mathbf{e}_1 = (1, 0, 0)$, $\mathbf{e}_2 = (0, 1, 0)$, $\mathbf{e}_3 = (0, 0, 1)$ be the vertexes of the two-dimensional simplex.

Lemma. For the QSO W (4), the following assertions true:

(i) The face $\Gamma_{\{2,3\}}$ of the simplex S^2 are invariant set;

(ii) $\text{Fix}(W) = \left\{ (1, 0, 0), \left(\frac{1}{3}, 0, \frac{2}{3}\right), \left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3}, 0\right), \left(\frac{1}{5}, \frac{2}{5}, \frac{2}{5}\right) \right\}$;

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